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**New species of the genus *Parameira* SEIDLITZ, 1868
(Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Entiminae:
Otiorrhynchini) from Greece**

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Abstract: New species of the genus *Parameira*, subgenus *Stierlinia* DESBROCHERS, 1909, *P. saosensis* **sp. n.** from North Aegean Island of Samothrace, and *P. peloponnesensis* **sp. n.** from Kyllini Mountains in northern Peloponnese, are described.

Key words: Coleoptera, Curculionidae, *Parameira*, new species, Greece.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Parameira* was established by SEIDLITZ (1868) to accommodate *Stomodes rudis* BOHEMAN, 1842 and newly then discovered *Parameira setosa* SEIDLITZ, 1868. The systematic position of this genus was never clear, MAGNANO and OSELLA 1971 referred *Parameira* to as a genus transitional between Otiorrhynchini SCHOENHERR, 1826 and Peritelini LACORDAIRE, 1863. I hereby follow common viewpoint and place *Parameira* in Otiorrhynchini, however, discussion concerning systematic position of the genus and generally relationship of Otiorrhynchini and Peritelini is far beyond the scope of the present paper. Currently thirteen *Parameira*-species are known (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2023) (including two species hereby described, and three species placed in the newly described subgenus *Clypeomeira* DAVIDIAN & GÜLTEKIN, 2023). All species of *Parameira* are narrowly distributed in north-eastern Mediterranean and Black Seas basins from Italy to Crimea and Caucasus, only parthenogenetic *P. gebleri* FAUST, 1893 is more widely distributed in Siberia. Species of *Parameira* are scarcely represented in collections due to this narrow range of distribution, and also because of cryptic way of life. During 2023 collecting trip to Samothrace Island a new species was discovered, which is described below. Furthermore, it turned out that specimens collected in 2012 on the Peloponnese, until now determined as *P. coronata* (STIERLIN, 1872) (which is known from the same peninsula), actually represent a distinct, undescribed species.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The width of the rostrum is defined as the pterygial span, i.e. the distance between the outer margins of the pterygia. “Pterygia projecting” means “pterygia” extending from the outline of the rostrum in the dorsal view. The stack photos were taken with a Leica M205C stereomicroscope with an attached JVC KYF75 digital camera and subsequently montaged using the AutoMontage software by Syncroscopy. Body length was measured from the anterior margin of the eyes to the elytral apex. Rostrum length was measured from the anterior margins of the eyes to the anterior part of the epistome. The genitalia are stored in a microvial with glycerine pinned under a card bearing the specimen (occasionally, damaged part are glued to the card with specimen); “ht” denotes holotype. ; “\” separates data concerning different specimens. Since the border between frons and epifrons is unclear in large majority of species, I still prefer to use general term “dorsal wall of rostrum”.

Acronyms: BIAL – collection of P.Z. Białooki, Sopot, Poland; USMB – collection of the Upper Silesian Museum in Bytom (curator R. Dobosz), Poland; WANA – collection of Marek Wanat, Wrocław University, Poland.

RESULTS

Subfamily Entiminae SCHÖENHERR, 1823

Tribe Otiorhynchini SCHÖENHERR, 1826

Genus *Parameira* SEIDLITZ, 1868 (type species *Stomodes rudis* BOHEMAN, 1842)

Subgenus *Stierlinia* DESBROCHERS, 1909 (type species *Cathormiocerus syriacus* STIERLIN, 1885)

***Parameira (Stierlinia) saosensis* sp. n.**

<https://zoobank.org/NomenclaturalActs/B76A06F0-4F90-4F8A-BFCB-FB2322AF8116>

(Figs. 1–5)

Material examined: holotype male dissected: 01.06.2023 NE Greece, N Samothrace Island, N Saos Mts. 1410 m, 40.4690N, 25.5830E, leg. P.Z. Białooki [BIAL] \ Paratypes: as ht, 37 exx. [BIAL; USMB; WANA].

Diagnosis. The new species is recognizable at first glance due to lack of raised setae on head, prothorax and elytra (Fig. 1,2); only on declivity scales are slightly raised. Moreover, scales arranged in single rows on interstices are subsodiametric in contrast to all other species of the genus which have raised elongate, seta-like scales (*P. peritelina* (PESARINI, 1970) has subsodiametric to weakly elongate scales but differs instantly from the new species in very narrow tarsi with third segment weakly broader than second). Also scales on pronotal disc are subcircular, precisely recumbent, thus resembling flat tubercles, condition unknown in whole genus to date; and strikingly robust tibiae, subparallel-sided in dorsal view, not constricted subapically. It is most similar to *P. peloponnesensis* sp. n. from Peloponnese, see diagnosis of the latter for details.

Description. Male: size range 4.0-5.1 mm (ht 4.7 mm); black, antennae and tarsi in part brown; whole body, except for funicle with club and tarsi, densely covered with greyish recumbent subsodiametric matt scales.

Rostrum markedly transverse (length 0.8 width), clearly separated from head, dorsal wall hardly at angle to head; pterygia large but indistinctly projecting; whole rostrum (except for

epistome and narrow area around it; as well as scrobes with antennal sockets) covered with dense recumbent weakly elongate broad scales completely obscuring surface; anterior part of the dorsal wall of rostrum distinctly declivous, subparallel-sided, narrow, slightly below 0.5 pterygial span; epistome fairly strongly convex, moderately narrowly crescentic; hind part of the dorsal wall of rostrum behind antennal insertions almost in a plane with interocular region; median sulcus hardly recognizable, reaching to hind margins of eyes; prementum slightly transverse, fairly small (maxillae in part visible), distinctly evenly concave, with 3 pairs of protruding hairs along middle portion of lateral margins.

Head moderately strongly transverse, $1.4 \times$ broader than rostrum minimum width; interocular area moderately strongly convex transversally due to lateral eyes; fovea not recognizable due to dense scales completely obscuring surface; eyes small indistinctly over 0.5 interocular distance, subcircular, weakly convex, markedly protruding from head convexity; temples subequally long as eyes; ventral wall of rostrum covered with fairly sparse narrow scales, as a result surface well visible.

Antennae moderately slender; scape very slightly curved, moderately strongly evenly widened, distally not clavate; densely covered with recumbent scales obscuring surface, and weakly yet distinctly raised arched elongate scales; each of first two funicle segments ca. $2.3 \times$ longer than broad, first slightly broader and somewhat longer than second; third segment subsodiametric, segments 4-7 slightly to moderately transverse; club twice as long as broad, as long as three and half distal funicle segments combined.

Prothorax slightly ($1.1 \times$) transverse, laterally moderately strongly rounded, widest in middle; anterior margin subequally long as base; longitudinally very weakly evenly convex; disc covered with fairly large pit-like punctures, each entirely covered with large subsodiametric recumbent scale; interspaces subequally long as scales diameter, covered with dense small broad recumbent scales fully obscuring surface; fringe along hind margin of pronotum consisting of large subsodiametric horizontal scales much resembling those in pronotal punctures, but slightly larger.

Elytra $1.65 \times$ longer than broad, distinctly ovate, widest in basal quarter, very weakly almost rectilinearly converging to ca. distal quarter, apically narrowly rounded (Fig. 1); longitudinally moderately weakly evenly convex; declivity fairly strongly convex, somewhat overhanging; striae fully obscured by vestiture, unclearly impressed, consisting of fairly small well delimited subsodiametric punctures; interspaces subequal to punctures diameter; interstices slightly wider than striae, flat; whole elytra covered with very dense greyish recumbent small subsodiametric scales totally obscuring surface; interstices with single row of large (ca. twice as long as scales throughout elytra) recumbent subsodiametric to slightly elongate scales, somewhat larger and slightly raised on declivity.

Legs moderately long, robust (Fig. 1); covered with very dense small recumbent subsodiametric scales fully obscuring surface, and distinctly larger, weakly to moderately elongate slightly raised scales; protibiae thick in dorsal view; distal comb consisting of long moderately dense bright brown setae; mucro fairly long, well visible, bright brown; hind tibiae very thick, subparallel-sided along whole length (in dorsal view); mucro well-developed; tibial spurs well-developed 1-1-2; tarsi moderately robust; second tarsite moderately strongly transverse; third bilobed segment large; onychium broad, its projecting portion subequal to length of preceding tarsite.

Ventrites covered with dense recumbent scales similar to those on elytra, completely obscuring surface, and with distinctly raised moderately sparse subparallel-sided scales $4-5 \times$ longer than wide, with fairly strong lustre; first ventrite broadly shallowly impressed; last ventrite slightly over $1.6 \times$ broader than long.

Aedeagus typical of *Parameira*; pedon $4.3 \times$ longer than broad, slightly (ca. $1.05 \times$) shorter than apodemes (Fig. 3); subparallel-sided along middle half, basally and subapically moderately strongly tapering, apex even slightly stronger so, narrowly subtriangular; somewhat irregularly bent (Fig. 4); parameres very short.

Female. Female differs from male in elytra, and head with rostrum, more robust; prothorax somewhat stronger transverse; elytra much broader, laterally stronger rounded, longitudinally very weakly convex; first ventrite not impressed; legs, particularly hind tibiae markedly less robust.

Female 8th sternite subisodiametric, distally hardly excised, with protruding dark hairs; spiculum ventrale somewhat over $3 \times$ longer than sternite; ovipositor consisting of short wide moderately tapering gonocoxites with small subapical transverse styli; spermatheca slender (Fig. 5), cornu subparallel-sided, distally somewhat stronger arched than basally.

Ecology. All specimens were collected well above upper forest line under weakly embedded stones at an altitude ca. 1400 m in a dry and hot place with scanty herbaceous vegetation.

Distribution. Only known from locus typicus and most probably endemic to Samothrace Island.

Etymology. The name (adjective) is patronymic, after locus typicus, Saos Mountains on the North Aegean Greek Island of Samothrace.

***Parameira (Stierlinia) peloponnesensis* sp. n.**

<https://zoobank.org/NomenclaturalActs/D0AD9D93-D1E5-430B-BEB4-9E8871FAE9A1>

(Figs. 6–10)

Material examined: holotype male dissected: 05.06.2012 S Greece, N Peloponnese, Kyllini Mts. > 2000 m, leg. P.Z. Białooki [BIAL]. Paratypes: as ht, but 04.06.2012, 1 ex \ as ht, 16 exx. [BIAL; USMB; WANA].

Diagnostic description. Male: *Parameira peloponnesensis* **sp. n.** can only be confused with *P. saosensis* **sp. n.** from Samothrace Island. *P. peloponnesensis* **sp. n.** differs from *P. coronata* STIERLIN, 1872, which is also known from Peloponnese, in less raised weakly elongate elytral scales; more slender elytra, longitudinally distinctly less convex, with less sloped declivity in particular; and the structure of male and female genitalia. *P. peloponnesensis* **sp. n.** differs from *P. saosensis* **sp. n.** in strikingly less robust tibiae, hind distally evidently constricted in dorsal view; tarsi very slender, third bilobed segment only slightly broader than second tarsite (Figs. 6, 7); aedeagus (Figs. 8, 9) regularly arched, distal part of apex shortly subtrapezoidal, sharply discontinuous with basal part, less downcurved; punctures on prothoracic disc with somewhat raised elongate subparallel-sided brown scale; weakly raised scales along interstices arranged in single rows weakly yet clearly elongate; fringe along hind margin of pronotal disc consisting of weakly yet distinctly elongate scales. Spermatheca (Fig. 10) very similar to that in *P. saosensis* **sp. n.**, with cornu slightly stronger curved distally and corpus more slender. *P. peloponnesensis* **sp. n.** differs instantly from *P. peritelina* PESARINI, 1970 (both species share very narrow tarsi) in pronotal raised scales strikingly narrower, several times narrower than scales forming hind prothoracic fringe (in *P. peritelina* both types of scales are subequally broad); protibiae in both sexes distinctly downcurved apically (protibiae hardly downcurved), and in distinctly stronger convex declivity, markedly overhanging vs. hardly overhanging in *P. peritelina*. *P. peloponnesensis* **sp. n.** differs from *P. coronata* STIERLIN, 1872, which is also known from Peloponnese, in less raised weakly elongate elytral scales; more slender elytra, longitudinally distinctly less convex, with less sloped declivity in particular; and the structure of male and female genitalia. Size range 4.1-5.1 mm.

Ecology. All specimens were found under stones at altitude ca. 2000 m in a place with scanty vegetation.

Distribution. *Parameira peloponnesensis* sp. n. is known exclusively from locus typicus in Kyllini Mountains in northern Peloponnese, where it is most likely endemic.

Etymology. The specific adjective is patronymic, after Peloponnese Peninsula.

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Fig. 1. *Parameira saosensis* sp. n., male habitus.

Fig. 2. *Parameira saosensis* sp. n., female habitus.

Fig. 3. *Parameira saosensis* sp. n., aedeagus ventral view.

Fig. 4. *Parameira saosensis* sp. n., aedeagus profile.

Fig. 5. *Parameira saosensis* sp. n., spermatheca.

Fig. 6. *Parameira peloponnesensis* sp. n., male habitus.

Fig. 7. *Parameira peloponnesensis* sp. n., female habitus.

Fig. 8. *Parameira peloponnesensis* sp. n., aedeagus ventral view.

Fig. 9. *Parameira peloponnesensis* sp. n., aedeagus profile.

Fig. 10. *Parameira peloponnesensis* **sp. n.**, spermatheca.

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